

On Certain Modes of the Protoberberine Ring Cleavage in the Biogenesis of Isoquinoline Alkaloids

S. Prasad, A. K. Wahi and S. Ghosal

A common hypothetical route to the genesis of certain group of isoquinoline alkaloids, such as the α -naphthaphenanthridine, phthalide isoquinoline, and protopine, involving prior N-methylation of the protoberberine precursor is envisaged. Supporting evidence has been gained from the *in vitro* transformation of canadine methochloride to chelerythrine and other products.

The co-occurrence¹ of the protoberberines, the α -naphthaphenanthridines, the phthalide isoquinolines, and the protopines, in several plant species (Table I) has often been a matter of comment. It is, therefore, of more than passing interest that the alkaloids of the above sub-groups are regarded to be derived from the protoberberines².

TABLE I

Co-occurrence of Certain Groups of Isoquinoline Alkaloids

Species	Types			
	α -Naphthaphenanthridine	Phthalide isoquinoline	Protoberberine	Protopine
<i>Chelidonium majus</i>	Chelidonine, Chelerythrine, Sanguinarine, Methoxychelidonine.	—	Coptisine Berberine	α - and β -Alloeryptopine, Protopine.
<i>Stylophorum diphyllum</i>	Chelidonine	—	1-Stylophine	Protopine
<i>Sanguinaria canadensis</i>	Chelerythrine Sanguinarine Oxysanguinarine	—	—	α - and β -Alloeryptopine, Protopine.
<i>Hydrastis canadensis</i>	—	Hydrastine	Berberine Canadine.	—

The currently accepted route to the genesis of the above types of isoquinoline alkaloids is presented here with the aid of structures (I-VI). There are ample experimental support for the validity of the biogenetic scheme (I-VI). Thus, dl-stylophine-3-C¹⁴ (I) fed to *Chelidonium majus* plants was shown to give radioactive coptisine (II)² and chelidonine (III)³.

1. J. Stanek and R. H. F. Manske, in 'The Alkaloids : Chemistry and Physiology', Ed. Manske and Holmes, A.P., Vol. IV, 1954, p. 176.
2. cf., A. R. Battersby, Proc. 3. Internationales Symp. Biochem. u. Physiol. der. Alkaloide, Akademie-Verlag, Berlin, 1966, p. 295.
3. E. Leete and J. B. Murril, *Phytochemistry*, 1967, **6**, 231.

Degradation experiments indicated the incorporation of the intact precursor (I) to (II) and (III). Again, the observations that reticuline was incorporated⁴ intact into narcotine and that the lactone carbonyl group of the latter was derived from the N-methyl group of reticuline, indicate the prior formation of a protoberberine, probably scoulerine (V) from reticuline (IV), and subsequent oxidation of (V) to afford narcotine (VI).

All these results are in excellent agreement with the proposed intermediacy² of a protoberberine entity (of the type I) enroute to α -naphthaphenanthrindine, protopine, and phthalide isoquinoline bases. However, further work is necessary to determine the mechanism of cleavage of the protoberberine C-ring (I) and the eventual ring-closure reactions.

We wish to report results of a few transformation reactions in this series which form the basis of certain modes of the protoberberine ring-cleavage envisaged herein.

One possible mode of ring cleavage could be by way of the N-oxide (VII)⁵⁻⁷. Bond scission at the dotted lines (a-c) in (VII) in presence of suitable red-ox systems would lead to the aforementioned three sub-groups of the isoquinoline alkaloids (II, III and VIII).

4. A. R. Battersby and M. Hirst, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 669.

5. A. Chatterjee and S. Ghosal, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 123.

6. E. Wenkert, *Exper.*, 1954, **10**, 346.

7. S. Ghosal and B. Mukherjee, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **31**, 2284.

The protoberberines of the type (I) are, in fact, very susceptible to autoxidation and the two most likely points of attack during this reaction are the two benzylic carbons,

—C₈ and C₁₃. Thus, both canadine (tetrahydroberberine) and tetrahydropalmitine autoxidize slowly to berberine and palmitine, respectively. This reaction, of course, does not preclude the formation of the corresponding *tert*-amineoxides in presence of reagents suitable for the

N-oxide formation. We have tested these possibilities using oxygen and peracetic acid as the oxidants. Canadine and tetrahydropalmitine upon oxygenation in aqueous acetic acid gave berberine and palmitine, respectively. Oxidation with peracetic acid also afforded berberine and palmitine plus the corresponding amineoxides as minor products. Rearrangement of the N-oxides⁸ with ferrous sulphate and acetic acid gave, contrary to expectation, only the tertiary bases in almost quantitative yield. Indeed, not even a trace of the corresponding ring-cleaved product could be detected from several sets of experiments. These observations obviously render the N-oxide intermediate less likely as a precursor for the genesis of the α -naphthaphenanthridine, the phthalide isoquinoline, and the protopine bases.

Of the other possibilities remaining for a facile C-ring cleavage of the protoberberine (I), the simplest and the most attractive one is by way of the corresponding metho-cation. It is of interest in this connection to note the conversion of the tetrahydroberberine metho-cation (IX) into the anhydro-base (X) first observed by Pyman⁹ which represents transformation from the berberine to the cryptopine type¹⁰. This evidence together with the co-presence of canadine metho-cation and γ -homochelidonine (β -allocryptopine) in *Zanthoxylum brachyacanthum*, and the singular absence of any secondary amine analogue in nature connote the significance of N-methylation in the entitled reaction.

When 1-canadine was the starting material, Pyman did indeed obtain two compounds (X) and (XI) in presence of a base. The actual transformation of (X) to β -allocryptopine was carried out by Haworth and Perkin¹¹. They observed an unusual rearrangement on heating the N-oxide of (X) with mixed hydrochloric and acetic acids when the amine oxide (XII) was converted to β -allocryptopine (XIII). This rearrangement was further utilized for the synthesis of protopine and cryptopine by the same authors.

The above two analogies may, profitably, be grouped together to envision the eventful role of N-methylation in the genesis of the isoquinoline alkaloids mentioned here.

8. Rearrangement of this type was first investigated by Horning *et al.* (M. S. Fish, N. M. Johnson, and E. C. Horning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5892.)

9. F. L. Pyman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **103**, 817.

10. It is apparent that (X) is liable to transform into (XI) and *vice-versa*.)

11. R. D. Haworth and W. H. Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 445.

We desired to extend the transformation of the protoberberines into the α -naphthaphenanthridine stage. For this purpose we repeated the base-catalyzed transformation of canadine metho-chloride. The product a mixture of (X) and (XI), was converted without separation into the corresponding amineoxides¹². Treatment of this product with ferrous sulphate and acetic acid gave at least three components as were detected by paper and thin layer chromatography. The component having R_f , 0.73 (Partridges' solvent system was used) showed striking similarity to chelerythrine in its physical and chemical properties¹³, λ_{max}^{EtOH} 240 (log ϵ , 3.92) and 288 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 3.81); m.p. and m.m.p. of the picrate, 236-8°. The most reasonable conclusion that may be drawn from the above results is expressed here in terms of a hypothetical common route (Scheme A) to the genesis of the aforementioned three sub-groups¹⁴ of isoquinoline alkaloids.

Scheme A

Biogenesis of Isoquinoline Alkaloids involving Prior N-Methylation

Department of Pharmaceutics,
Banaras Hindu University,
Varanasi-5.

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12. Paper chromatography, however, showed only one spot, R_f 0.88.

13. Details of this investigation will be reported soon.

14. Several other possibilities, e.g., the conversion of protopine N-oxides to rhoeadine type bases and *vice-versa*, are currently being investigated in this laboratory.